

Benchmarking on improvement and site-adaptation techniques for modeled solar radiation datasets

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Abstract

High-accuracy solar radiation data are needed in almost every solar energy project for bankability. Time series of solar irradiance components that spans decades can be supplied by satellite-derived irradiance or by reanalysis models, with very various types of uncertainty associated to the specific approaches taken and quality of boundary conditions information. In order to improve the reliability of these modeled datasets, comparison with ground measurements over a short period of time can be used for correcting some aspects, bias mainly, of the modeled data by using different methodologies; this procedure is known as site adaptation. Therefore, a benchmarking exercise that uses different site adaptation techniques was proposed within the Task 16 IEA-PVPS activities. In this work, over ten different site-adaptation techniques have been used for assessing the accuracy improvement, using ten different datasets covering both satellite-derived and reanalysis solar radiation data. The effectiveness of these methods is found not universal or spatially homogeneous, but in general, it can be stated that significant improvements can be achieved eventually in most sites and datasets.

34 Keywords: satellite-derived solar radiation, site adaptation, bankability of data for solar
35 projects, modeled solar radiation data

36 **1. Introduction**

37 Solar power deployments, such as photovoltaics (PV) or concentrating solar power
38 (CSP) plants, require high-quality decade-long time series of solar radiation data for
39 both technical (planning dimensioning and designing stages) and financial aspects of
40 the project. The long-term variability of solar resources plays a significant role in
41 estimating the probability of exceedance of the future energy yields of a solar power
42 plant, and it influences the financial conditions that the project is likely to receive
43 (Fernández-Peruchena et al., 2018). Notwithstanding, due to the significant intra-day
44 and inter-annual variability of solar irradiance, the solar resource assessment should
45 consider time series, instead of only considering the climatological averages. Reliable
46 and bankable solar radiation data should include at least time series of direct normal
47 irradiance (DNI) for CSP projects, and global horizontal irradiance (GHI) or plane of
48 array (POA) global irradiance for the PV ones (Sengupta et al., 2017). Additionally,
49 high-quality diffuse horizontal irradiance (DHI) data are also desirable and might be
50 required in specific solar projects and applications.

51
52 Long-term time series of the solar radiation components at the Earth's surface can be
53 modelled by many methodologies based on satellite imagery or numerical weather
54 model reanalysis. The use of satellite-based models is currently most common in
55 carrying out both solar resource mapping and site-specific solar irradiance data
56 generation, since this approach has achieved a high degree of maturity and reliability.
57 Solar engineers' extensive modeling experience in producing operational satellite-
58 derived irradiance can be traced back to the late 1980s (Cano et al., 1986; Polo et al.,
59 2008; Polo and Perez, 2019). The works that aim to validate, improve and apply these
60 satellite-based methods are still on-going today and are being reported regularly in the
61 relevant scientific and industry communities (Cros et al., 2019; Merrouni et al., 2017;
62 Perez et al., 2017; Pfeifroth et al., 2017; Porfirio and Ceballos, 2017; Qu et al., 2017;
63 Riihelä, 2018; Tang et al., 2016; Thomas et al., 2016; Urraca et al., 2017; Yang, 2019,
64 2018; Yang and Boland, 2019; Yang and Perez, 2019). High-quality, satellite-derived
65 irradiance datasets are made freely available by several providers, such as PVGIS
66 (Amillo et al., 2014), CM-SAF (Kothe et al., 2019; Posselt et al., 2012), or NSRDB
67 (Sengupta et al., 2018). In addition, the quality of the latest reanalysis data has
68 improved significantly (Urraca et al., 2018), although the specific validation exercise
69 was performed using daily data and the hourly results are still unclear. Nevertheless,
70 large number of recent works highlights the interest on this topic (Feng and Wang,
71 2019; Huld et al., 2018; Peng et al., 2019; Perdigoão et al., 2016; Ramirez Camargo and

72 Dorner, 2016; Salazar et al., 2020; Tahir et al., 2020; Trolliet et al., 2018; Zib et al.,
73 2012).

74

75 That said, despite the improvements and quality gained in the recent years, various
76 types of uncertainties are still embedded in modeled solar irradiance datasets,
77 particularly owing to the uniformity of the data-generating process. Stated differently,
78 when a model retrieves solar irradiance at a specific site some uncertainties are
79 involved. Systematic errors in the models, limitations in the spatial and temporal
80 resolutions, uncertainty in the atmospheric data that affects the radiative transfer
81 process are, among others, some of the major sources of uncertainty that can result in
82 biases or deviations in the modeled data.

83

84 Validation results in the literature for GHI and DNI, either satellite-derived or
85 reanalysis-based, are very difficult to summarize. A huge amount of studies can be
86 found elsewhere. Many providers and models report uncertainties that can vary a lot
87 depending on the geographic area, the intrinsic characteristics of the model and on the
88 quality of ground data used for validation. In order to illustrate this variability, just a
89 few recent validation results are given next. Uncertainties in the range of -4 to 9%
90 MBD (Mean Bias deviation) and 17-50% RMSD (Root Mean Square Deviation) for
91 hourly GHI were reported with the eastern Meteosat satellite (Amillo et al., 2014). In
92 India, SARA-E satellite-based estimations resulted in 10-20% overestimation of the
93 surface incoming solar radiation (Riihelä, 2018). In Chile, nearly unbiased hourly GHI
94 with 20% RMSD was recently estimated using GOES satellite imagery (Molina et al.,
95 2017). Recent validation of the National Solar Radiation database (NSRBD) reported
96 RMSD ranges of 9-18% and 15-30% for hourly GHI and DNI, respectively (Yang, 2018).
97 The HelioClim-3 database reported 8% MBD and 20% RMSD for DNI estimations in
98 Morocco (Merrouni et al., 2017). Version 4 of the SUNY model has improved notably
99 its performance in both GHI and DNI (Perez et al., 2015). Therefore, quality, availability
100 and completeness of the ground data, topography and climatology of the site,
101 accuracy of the boundary conditions and input parameters (atmospheric composition,
102 cloud properties, etc.) play an important role in the uncertainty characterization of the
103 models for estimating solar radiation components.

104

105 In virtually every solar power project, and in many other applications, the preliminary
106 characterization of long-term solar resources is done by evaluating the modeled time
107 series of solar irradiance against short-term local ground measurements. Setting up a
108 high-quality, ground-based monitoring station at the project site is always
109 recommended for projects with significant financial investment. It is also highly
110 recommended to keep the station instruments properly calibrated and maintained.
111 The assessment of long-term data by comparing to local measurements could help in
112 terms of uncertainty quantification and mitigating the financing risk of the project

113 (Armansperg et al., 2015; Fernández-Peruchena et al., 2018; Fernández Peruchena et
114 al., 2016; Guerreiro et al., 2016; Hirsch et al., 2017; Meyer and Schwandt, 2017; Polo et
115 al., 2017, 2016a; Richter et al., 2015). Moreover, a reasonable period of ground
116 measurements (usually a year) can be used to remove bias, and thus correct and
117 improve the long-term solar radiation time series by different techniques. These
118 techniques aim to find a relationship between the ground and modeled data that can
119 be extrapolated to the past, as a means for minimizing the statistical deviations. This
120 process of calibration or correction of modeled data by including observational data
121 has been used in the retrievals of other meteorological variables (wind velocity,
122 precipitation, etc.). In the field of energy meteorology, such correction procedures
123 have been frequently termed *site adaptation* techniques (Polo et al., 2016b). Several
124 example techniques that have been applied to improve the goodness of solar radiation
125 time series can be found in the recent literature (Frank et al., 2018; Mazonra Aguiar et
126 al., 2019; Perez et al., 2010; Polo et al., 2015; Tahir et al., 2020).

127

128 In the framework of the Task 16 of IEA-PVPS (<http://www.iea-pvps.org/index.php?id=389>)
129 and Task V of IEA-SolarPACES entitled “Solar Resource for High Penetration and Large
130 Scale Applications”, several activities are being addressed in benchmarking, models
131 assessment and improving knowledge of modeling solar radiation components.
132 Improvement in measuring protocols, gap filling, and quality check of ground data and
133 benchmarking of models are, among others, activities focused on improving the
134 bankability of solar radiation products. In this context, benchmarking and reviewing of
135 site-adaptation techniques for solar resource data are stated as activities of interest
136 (Remund et al., 2017). Under this framework, several task participants are developing
137 different techniques and procedures for improving and correcting the modeled
138 datasets, for various satellite-derived and reanalysis datasets, in order to have a
139 sample of modeled solar radiation data that can typify the different types of
140 uncertainties.

141

142 A first benchmarking exercise has been developed by four teams of scientists, and its
143 methodology and results are reported here. Each team has implemented one or
144 several site adaptation techniques, according to their previous experience and skills.
145 All these methodologies have been applied in a blind exercise to 10 different datasets
146 (consisted of pairs of ground and model sets of data of the solar irradiance
147 components: GHI, DNI and DHI).

148

149 For the present needs, a blind exercise is justified to protect some of the techniques
150 that are, or could be become, commercial. This study aims at performing a pure
151 statistical exercise to explore the capability of a given technique to improve a dataset
152 using a small part of the observations. Therefore ground and model datasets, and
153 techniques, are selected following these simple rules: covering quite different climates,

154 using mostly free and open-source modeled and ground data, and selecting those site
155 adaptation techniques with enough details in the literature for easy implementation.
156 This paper acts as a report for those findings.

157

158 **2. Description of the methodologies and approaches**

159

160 Different methodologies have been tested in this work for site adaptation of solar
161 radiation data. Some of them originate from other subdomain of meteorology (Piani et
162 al., 2010; Wilcke et al., 2013). This section provides a general description of the
163 fundamentals of those methodologies considered in this work. It is emphasized that
164 more site adaptation techniques do exist, and some of them were described in Polo et
165 al. 2016; hence, the present contribution should not be considered exhaustive. The
166 procedures for using these techniques can be applied to either the entire dataset, or
167 subsets of data that are divided according to solar elevation or sky classification, for
168 instance. In order to emulate a realistic situation in resource assessment for solar
169 projects, each site-adaptation procedure has been carried out using data from the
170 latest year available at each site, and each adapted series has been compared with
171 measured data spanning the entire history of that site.

172

173 **2.1 Linear regression bias removal**

174

175 The bias removal using a linear regression model aims at finding a linear relationship
176 between the measured and modeled data, which often can result in an improved
177 coefficient of determination of the pair of random variables. This simple methodology
178 is quite commonly used to correct satellite-derived solar radiation data, showing good
179 results in presence of large seasonal bias (Mazorra Aguiar et al., 2019; Polo et al.,
180 2016b, 2015). Linear least squares fitting is performed between the modeled data (x_m)
181 and observations (x_o) over a selected period of time (e.g., one year) to obtain the
182 slope (a) and the y-intercept (b). The bias-removal procedure for the fitting data can
183 be expressed using the following equation:

184

$$185 \quad y = x_m - [(a-1) x_o + b]. \quad (1)$$

186

187 Such expression of y and x_m results in a linear function f that can be used to transform
188 all the historical modeled data into new corrected data, y_c .

189

$$190 \quad y_c = f(x_m), \quad (2)$$

191

192 where f represents the linear function resulting from fitting the corrected y_c values
193 versus the original y . This procedure has similarities with the Measured-Related-

194 Predict (MCP) methods (Carta et al., 2013). In the context of this work this method will
195 be called LIN-FIT for better comparison with the other methodologies used here.

196

197 2.2 Quantile mapping (QM)

198

199 The quantile mapping (QM) technique has been employed in climate modeling and
200 meteorology for correcting the distribution of a modeled parameter by comparing it
201 against the empirical distribution of the observations (Déqué et al., 2007; Ines and
202 Hansen, 2006). The approach seeks to transform the data to a probability domain
203 (quantiles) and applies the inverse transformation using the cumulative distribution
204 function (CDF) of the observational data to obtain the corrected data (Déqué et al.,
205 2007),

206

$$207 \quad y_c = \text{CDF}_o^{-1}[\text{CDF}_m(x_m)], \quad (3)$$

208

209 where CDF_o and CDF_m are the cumulative distribution functions of the observed and
210 modeled data, respectively.

211 The quantiles of modeled and observed data can be computed by the full empirical
212 non-parametric distribution or by a fitted theoretical parametric distribution
213 (Feigenwinter et al., 2018; Piani et al., 2010; Themeßl et al., 2012).

214

215 2.3 Quantile delta mapping (QDM)

216

217 The quantile delta mapping (QDM) bias-correction method is an extension of the
218 conventional QM technique (Cannon, 2018; Cannon et al., 2015). The algorithm
219 preserves the model-projected relative changes in quantiles, and additionally, corrects
220 the systematic quantile biases of the modeled data with respect to the observed
221 values. The bias-adjustment of the modeled values for the reference period is the
222 same as the traditional QM technique. With respect to the target variable, two
223 corrections are applied (additive and multiplicative):

224

$$225 \quad y_c = x_m + \text{CDF}_o^{-1}[\text{CDF}_m(x_m)] - \text{CDF}_m^{-1}[\text{CDF}_m(x_m)], \quad (4)$$

$$226 \quad y_c = x_m \frac{\text{CDF}_o^{-1}[\text{CDF}_m(x_m)]}{\text{CDF}_m^{-1}[\text{CDF}_m(x_m)]}.$$

227

228 2.4 Cumulative distribution function-transform (CDF-T)

229

230 The CDF-T method performs QM based on the CDFs over the future period, thus,
231 allowing the CDF to change with respect to the reference period. It provides an
232 extension of the traditional QM method since the QM technique only transforms the
233 modeled values of the future period onto the CDF of the reference period
234 (Michelangeli et al., 2009).

235

236

237 2.5 Kernel density distribution mapping (KDM)

238

239 Kernel density distribution mapping (KDM) method uses a similar logic as QM, at least
240 algorithmically. In general, QM enables the bias-adjustment by transforming the
241 modeled values into quantiles, and then projecting them into data values in terms of
242 the quantile function (inverse CDF) of the observations (McGinnis et al., 2015). In KDM
243 the CDF and the CDF⁻¹ functions are expressed in terms of the kernel density estimator. The
244 probability density functions (PDF) of the modeled and the observed values are estimated non-
245 parametrically using kernel density estimation assuming a Gaussian kernel (Izenman, 2016).
246 Two slightly different versions of KDM have been used in this work. KDM-T and KDM-CS refer
247 to the application of the technique to the whole dataset and to subsets according to sky
248 conditions (clear or non-clear), respectively. KDMR is just KDM with an optimal bandwidth
249 algorithm.

250

251 2.6 Site-specific multiple regression (SIM)

252 This method is based on the multi-model inference (also known as ensemble) of multiple linear
253 regression models, through computing, comparing, and ranking an exhaustive list of models.
254 For the local adaptation of GHI, an exhaustive screening of the selected exogenous variables is
255 carried out, followed by a selection of a best model as per the Akaike information criterion
256 (AIC). The model is constructed through both the selected variables and their interactions; the
257 exogenous variables include clearness index of modeled GHI series (K_t , the ratio of GHI to top-
258 of-atmosphere solar irradiance on the same plane); relative air mass (m); modeled clear-sky
259 index (K_c , the ratio between modeled GHI and its corresponding value under clear-sky
260 conditions); and solar elevation angle. The clear-sky model used in this method is McClear
261 (Lefèvre et al., 2013), available through the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
262 (CAMS, <http://www.soda-pro.com/web-services/radiation/cams-mcclear>).

263 The methodology for the local adaptation of DNI is based on the previous adaptation of the
264 diffuse horizontal irradiance (DHI), because the ratio DHI to GHI (K , diffuse fraction) is known
265 to be reliably predictable from the following parameters (and their combinations): m , K_c , solar
266 elevation, and a fourth-order polynomial of Kt_m . Finally, DNI is calculated from both locally
267 adapted GHI and DHI by the closure equation, assuring the accomplishment of the
268 fundamental relations between these solar radiation components. Finally, the procedure is
269 applied separately for clear-sky and non-clear-sky days.

270 2.7 Sequential regressive-quantile mapping procedure (SIMEQ)

271 This method is a sequential application of two procedures of different nature. Firstly, the SIM
272 technique (described in the preceding subsection, 2.6) is applied, which is based on the
273 multimodel inference of multiple linear regression models. Secondly, a bias correction based
274 on empirical quantile mapping (eQM) is applied on both GHI and DNI adapted series. This
275 method consists in calibrating the simulated CDF by adding to the observed quantiles both the
276 mean delta change and the individual delta changes in the corresponding quantiles. Finally,
277 DHI is calculated from the locally adapted GHI and DNI, through the closure equation, thus
278 satisfying the fundamental relations between these solar radiation components.

279 The first procedure (i.e., the SIM method) can considerably reduce both the dispersion and the
280 deviation in CDF of the adapted solar irradiance series, with respect to the modeled ones. The
281 application of the second procedure (eQM) to the mentioned adapted series significantly
282 reduces the deviation in CDF, while maintaining or reducing the values of the dispersion
283 statistical indicators. Similar to the case of the SIM technique, this procedure is applied
284 separately to clear and non-clear-sky days.

285

286 2.8 Regressions using subsets of data

287 Specific regressions and fitting techniques can be also applied to subsets of data as a
288 site adaptation procedure. In this paper a methodology is used for correcting only GHI
289 where subsets of ground and modeled data are first classified into different ranges of
290 solar zenith angles and clear-sky index, K_{cs} (the ratio between the modeled GHI and its
291 corresponding value under clear-sky conditions). Solar zenith angles are divided into 5
292 groups in the range of 0-75° with intervals of 15°, whereas K_{cs} is divided into two
293 groups, namely lower and greater than 0.55. For each combination of groups (10
294 combinations in total), a pair of third-degree polynomial regressions are applied to the
295 last year of modeled and ground data - one for GHI and the other one for K_{cs} .
296 Moreover, two additional regressions (again one for GHI and one for K_{cs}) are
297 calculated from samples of the entire year (solar zenith angle between 0-75° and K_{cs}
298 between 0 and 1). This makes a total of 22 regressions. The one that minimizes the
299 relative bias is picked for this particular subsample.

300 3. Ground and modeled datasets

301 In order to benchmark the different site adaptation techniques, sites are selected from
302 locations under different climates, and covered by different networks of ground stations. In
303 addition, different types of modeled data (i.e., satellite-derived and reanalysis) are used. Most
304 of these data belong to different satellite-derived datasets, estimated using different methods,
305 and issued by various providers. Reanalysis data, on the other hand, cover two high-latitude
306 sites, where satellite images do not resolve. Table 1 summarizes the metadata of the selected
307 sites, which are drawn on the world map together with their climatic types in Figure 1. In this
308 regard, the datasets herein used belong to modeled data with very different uncertainties

309 corresponding to two different reanalyses, several satellite models with different approaches
 310 regarding the clear-sky transmittance, atmospheric information (aerosol optical depth or
 311 turbidity, water vapor and other components) and satellite imagery (different satellite
 312 platforms). Each dataset contains both the modeled and measured hourly values of the three
 313 basic solar radiation components (GHI, DNI and DHI). In addition, some, but not all, BSRN-
 314 recommended quality checks for ground data are performed (Long and Dutton, 2004), for both
 315 ground and model data. The reason is to allow the assessment of site adaptation methods as a
 316 “blind” statistical tool attempting to fit different model data to observational ones.

317 Table 1. Summary of sites with pair ground-model datasets for benchmarking

Site (code)	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	Elevation (m)	Climate	Period	Model type
Alice Springs (ASP)	-23.79	133.88	547	Hot desert, arid	2007-2013	Satellite
Boulder (BOU)	40.12	-105.23	1689	Cold semi-arid	2009-2015	Satellite
Tateno (TAT)	36.05	140.12	25	humid subtropical	2009-2015	Satellite
Tamanrasset (TAM)	22.79	5.52	1385	Hot desert, arid	2007-2011	Satellite
Carpentras (CAR)	44.08	5.05	100	Mediterranean	2007-2013	Satellite
Burns (BRN)	43.52	-119.02	1271	Cold semi-arid	2007-2013	Satellite
Kiruna (KIR)	67.48	20.41	424	subarctic	2008-2014	Reanalysis
Norrköping (NRK)	58.58	16.14	53	humid continental	2008-2014	Reanalysis
Visby (VIS)	57.67	18.34	49	oceanic	2008-2014	Satellite
Sede Boqer	30.86	34.77	500	Hot desert, arid	2006-2011	Satellite

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320 4. Deviations of the model datasets

321 The evaluation approach for the modeled datasets is described before presenting the
 322 results of the different site adaptation techniques. For assessment of model and site
 323 adaptation performance, three metrics are selected: mean bias deviation (MBD), root
 324 mean square deviation (RMSD) and Kolmogorov-Smirnov integral (KSI). The first two
 325 accuracy measures indicate bias and dispersion, whereas the third informs the
 326 similitude of CDFs of modeled and measured data (Gueymard, 2014). Table 2 shows
 327 the statistical metrics expressed in percent of all the modeled datasets (i.e. the original
 328 uncorrected datasets as delivered by the different models used) for the three
 329 components. Large ranges of bias, dispersion and similitude of distribution functions in
 330 the model dataset can be observed as a consequence of taking both the site
 331 characteristics and the approaches into account in the modeling. This is a good
 332 outcome from the study since the scope of this work is not the performance of models

333 retrieving solar radiation data but the capability of statistical methods to correct any
334 model according to short-term observational values.

335

336 Figure 1. Sites selected for benchmarking site adaptation methods.

337

338 5. Site adaptation assessment results

339 Different procedures for site adaptation (up to 12) based on the previously described
340 techniques (in Section 2) were used by four different teams in their attempt to
341 generate corrected or improved values of the 10 datasets. Table 3 summarizes the
342 characteristics of each procedure and details the team that employed each procedure.
343 In all cases, the most recent year of ground data was used to train the model whereas
344 the adaptation was applied to the whole period of the modeled dataset under
345 scrutiny. It should be noted that eQM-CS and KDM-CS methods differ from other
346 quantile mapping methodologies, since they are applied separately to the two subsets

347 of modeled data that had been obtained for each sky condition (clear or non clear-
 348 sky). Therefore, prior to the use of those methods a selection of model data was done
 349 using an algorithm for automatic detection of clear-sky instants. In the case of eQM-CS
 350 and KDM-CS, the clear-sky detection is done using a method proposed by Gueymard
 351 2013. The procedure requires DNI observations and concomitant DNI estimations
 352 under clear-sky conditions based on reliable aerosol optical depth (AOD) data. There is
 353 no perfect algorithm for a posteriori clear-sky identification in solar irradiance time
 354 series since any method may be affected by various sources of error, including
 355 inaccuracies in the input required. For instance, the computation of clear-sky
 356 components need of very accurate information of AOD and Precipitable water at least)
 357 (Gueymard, 2013; Gueymard et al., 2019). A very promising new model has been
 358 recently proposed in the literature for 1-min data (Bright et al., 2020). However the
 359 specific algorithm used in this work points the potential benefits of an accurate
 360 separation of clear and non clear-sky instants in site adaptation methodologies.

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Table 2. Statistical metrics for the performance of uncorrected modeled datasets.

Site	GHI (%)			DNI (%)			DHI (%)		
	MBD	RMSD	KSI	MBD	RMSD	KSI	MBD	RMSD	KSI
Alice Springs	0.0	12.2	49.1	-1.1	20.1	203.7	3.2	47.1	127.1
Boulder	0.1	25.8	92.3	-6.1	49.9	102.6	9.7	50.6	99.3
Tateno	-3.3	18.3	46.9	-5.5	32.8	81.6	-1.3	31.2	117.6
Tamanrasset	-5.9	16.8	75.4	-12.7	38.8	223.7	9.8	51.7	206.8
Carpentras	2.6	17.4	50.1	3.6	31.5	64.7	3.7	42.0	144.9
Burns	-1.0	26.9	78.6	5.8	37.7	109.8	-9.6	60.1	247.6
Kiruna	106.9	258.3	31.1	39.4	179.7	23.3	26.8	141.6	37.7
Norrkoping	36.6	172.2	21.6	-18.6	118.5	18.7	33.9	141.7	43.4
Visby	33.1	170.2	28.6	-11.3	123.3	21.2	25.5	138.0	52.5
Sede Boqer	-3.9	33.7	75.1	-15.3	42.4	207.7	19.2	59.6	334.1

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Table 3. Summary of site adaptation techniques and procedures.

Name	Type	Components	Observations	Team
eQM-T	Quantile Mapping	GHI,DNI,DHI	Empirical CDF	Team 1
eQM-CS	Quantile Mapping	GHI,DNI,DHI	Empirical CDF, separately to clear and non-clear-sky data	Team 1
KDM-T	Quantile Mapping	GHI,DNI,DHI	Kernel Density Distribution Mapping, limiting the maximum irradiance in the CDF to 5% over maximum observed	Team 1
KDM-CS	Quantile Mapping	GHI,DNI,DHI	Same as before but separately to clear and non-clear-sky data	Team 1
LIN-FIT	Regression	GHI,DNI,DHI	Simple linear fit	Team 2
CDF-T	Quantile Mapping	GHI,DNI,DHI	As described in section 2.4	Team 2

KDMR	Quantile Mapping	GHI,DNI,DHI	Kernel Density Distribution Mapping with optimal bandwidth	Team 2
QDM	Quantile Mapping	GHI,DNI,DHI	As described in section 2.3	Team 2
SIM	Multiple Regression	GHI,DNI,DHI	As described in section 2.6	Team 3
SIMEQ	Sequential	GHI,DNI,DHI	As described in section 2.7	Team 3
REG	Regression	GHI	As described in section 2.8	Team 4

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371

372 Figures 2, 3 and 4 show the statistical metrics of the performance of the eight site
 373 adaptation methods for the GHI, DNI and DHI components, respectively. The first
 374 entry, referred to as model, indicates the original uncorrected modeled data in order
 375 to allow proper comparison and to illustrate the relative improvement in performance
 376 generated by each site adaptation method.

377

378

379 Figure 2. Statistical metrics for benchmarking of site adaptation applied to GHI.

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382 Figure 3. Statistical metrics for benchmarking of site adaptation applied to DNI.

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385 Figure 4. Statistical metrics for benchmarking of site adaptation applied to DHI.

386 The benchmarking results for GHI show that bias is not successfully removed in all
 387 cases. In particular, modeled datasets having an originally low bias (< 1%) site do not
 388 benefit from any improvement, with the exception of some QM-based (CDF-T, KDMR,
 389 QDM) and multiple regression based (SIM, SIMEQ) methods. However, in the case of
 390 modeled data with significant bias (> 30%), most techniques generally result in MBD
 391 improvement compared to unprocessed model data resulting in a much lower MBD
 392 (<10%) for most of them, and even in negligible bias (<1%) in the case of KDMR.

393

394 RMSD is very slightly improved by most techniques, except in the case of modeled
395 datasets corresponding to the three sites (Kiruna, Norrköping, and Visby) at very high
396 latitude ($>55^\circ$), where the original modeled data are affected by substantial
397 uncertainty (Table 2), and where the site adaptation techniques induce a significant
398 decrease in random errors. At those sites with the lowest RMSD values ($< 20\%$), only
399 those methods based on multiple regression (SIM, SIMEQ) achieved RMSD reduction
400 (from 16.2% to 14.5%).

401

402 In the case of DNI, most of the methods are able to achieve significant improvement
403 over the highly negatively biased modeled data (with typical MBD of $\sim 15\%$), even
404 bringing down the MBD to below 3% with some of them (eQM-CS, KDM-T, SIM and
405 SIMEQ). The highly positively biased site (Kiruna, MBD = 39.5%) is satisfactorily
406 corrected by some methods, among which eQM-T and eQM-CS should be highlighted.
407 On the other hand, sites with moderate MBD (BOU and TAT, negatively bias at $\sim 5.8\%$,
408 and CAR and BRN, positively bias at $\sim 4.8\%$) are satisfactorily corrected by most
409 methods. Conversely, RMSD is more significantly improved by only some techniques.
410 In particular, sites with high RMSD (KIR, NRK and VIS, with RMSD $\sim 140\%$) are on
411 average improved by all methods, among which SIM and SIMEQ should be highlighted
412 because they reduce RMSD by half. At all other sites (typical RMSD $\sim 36\%$), only some
413 methods based both on QM (eQM-CS, KDM-T, KDM-CS) and multiple regression (SIM
414 and SIMEQ) achieve improvements.

415

416 For the case of DHI, the situation at high-bias sites (MBD $> 20\%$) is generally improved
417 by the site adaptation techniques, whereas very different results are obtained at low-
418 bias sites. Performance improvement in terms of RMSD is mainly observed for a few
419 datasets wherever the initial bias is large.

420

421 On the other hand, there are some methods that eventually show a characteristic bad
422 performance not observed at other sites. Thus, LIN-FIT, CDF-T, KDMR and QDM
423 showed slightly or remarkable improvement in GHI and DHI except at Tamanrasset
424 site. This particular behavior cannot be attributed to a particular site adaptation
425 method, so that other potential causes would need to be investigated, such as
426 subjective user interventions or impacts of the specific training year selected for those
427 methods.

428

429 KSI is a metric difficult to evaluate in general. Nevertheless, a general better
430 performance can be observed in the three components by all QM-based methods as
431 well as in SIMEQ (which uses an eQM procedure). Exceptions to this observation for
432 some methods (CDF-T, KDM-R and QDM) may be found for Tamanrasset (due probably
433 to unknown reasons beyond the methodology) and at very high-latitude sites.
434 Obtaining any improvement at the three high-latitude sites is very challenging because

435 their measured global irradiance can be positive at zero or negative sun elevation
 436 angles, and because the models selected for these sites were apparently highly
 437 uncertain.

438

439 Condensing the benchmarking and comparisons results in one unique and proper
 440 parameter might be questionable; however, in order to illustrate the results a unique
 441 metric called combined performance Index (CPI) can be used here (Gueymard, 2014).
 442 CPI is defined as a weighted sum of several metrics to combine information on the
 443 dispersion and on the distribution function similitude as well. That is,

444

$$445 \quad \quad \quad CPI = (KSI + OVER + 2 RMSE)/4. \quad (5)$$

446

447 Tables 4, 5 and 6 show the performance of the different site adaptation techniques for
 448 GHI, DNI and DHI, respectively, in terms of CPI (in percentage). In these tables, the row
 449 denoted as Raw Model and highlighted in bold refers to the original uncorrected
 450 model dataset. According to these results most methods resulted in improvement of
 451 the model datasets. There are, nevertheless, exceptions, such as the LIN-FIT method,
 452 that performs worse at Burns and at high-latitude sites. Despite the absence of any
 453 universal rule in the results, in several situations benefits can be obtained by
 454 separating the data into two subsets (clear and non-clear sky). In addition, the
 455 sequential use of methods, as occurs in the SIMEQ methodology, produces better
 456 performance. Quantile mapping based methodologies, in general, tend also to reduce
 457 the uncertainty.

458

459

460 Table 4. CPI (%) for GHI benchmarking results.

461

462

	ASP	BOU	TAT	TAM	CAR	BRN	KIR	NRK	VIS	SBO	P50*
Raw Model	25.5	54.0	23.7	39.7	25.2	46.0	138.1	91.5	92.3	45.6	45.8
eQM-T	18.6	21.4	17.5	20.7	45.0	52.6	77.7	70.1	71.6	30.6	37.8
eQM-CS	19.3	20.4	17.7	20.3	46.3	52.9	72.3	54.4	57.4	22.7	34.5
KDM-T	24.5	23.4	21.2	20.9	48.2	36.7	78.1	70.8	72.6	36.6	36.7
KDM-CS	22.0	20.0	20.6	17.6	40.3	37.5	73.8	56.7	59.5	39.6	38.6
LIN-FIT	20.5	42.7	20.5	163.7	24.5	67.8	190.3	122.7	141.5	53.3	60.6
CDF-T	14.7	19.6	13.9	158.3	21.4	27.3	60.2	72.5	46.6	32.7	30.0
KDMR	20.6	19.2	12.5	155.4	16.7	33.8	51.6	43.3	49.2	29.5	31.7
QDM	12.9	21.2	15.8	177.8	17.6	30.1	48.4	51.2	63.8	34.9	32.5
SIM	9.8	55.2	27.3	25.1	17.8	70.2	109.6	75.9	49.4	12.1	38.4
SIMEQ	12.9	34.1	15.8	16.8	15.9	33.8	51.1	46.0	42.8	8.4	25.3
REG	71.5	37.6	21.0	76.8	109.4	59.2	97.5	71.5	79.1	101.5	74.2

463 *Median of CPI for all sites

464
465
466
467

Table 5. CPI (%) for DNI benchmarking results.

	ASP	BOU	TAT	TAM	CAR	BRN	KIR	NRK	VIS	SBO	P50*
Raw Model	109.3	70.3	53.5	129.0	37.8	69.0	97.4	64.0	67.0	121.2	81.9
eQM-T	58.3	36.4	28.3	32.8	42.3	62.5	90.8	67.1	68.5	33.6	52.1
eQM-CS	43.1	30.5	27.3	29.4	24.5	63.6	73.6	42.4	49.2	24.7	40.8
KDM-T	64.0	56.7	26.1	57.9	44.1	58.2	95.8	61.7	68.9	44.8	57.8
KDM-CS	56.7	30.7	22.0	34.8	40.2	53.4	71.1	39.6	49.7	36.1	43.4
LIN-FIT	80.7	118.9	31.2	54.5	50.2	131.5	93.8	129.0	123.4	94.6	90.8
CDF-T	40.0	40.0	26.9	76.5	47.1	49.6	65.9	56.6	153.5	48.1	60.4
KDMR	56.7	35.7	28.6	76.9	43.8	63.2	66.1	69.7	163.0	60.9	66.5
QDM	39.1	40.0	28.0	121.8	39.8	57.2	93.5	61.0	370.4	37.4	88.8
SIM	31.5	103.1	43.8	82.1	106.2	157.3	193.1	147.7	88.3	53.0	100.6
SIMEQ	21.4	54.5	35.5	30.6	31.0	41.0	78.7	53.5	49.5	18.5	41.4

468 *Median of CPI for all sites

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Table 6. CPI for DHI benchmarking results.

	ASP	BOU	TAT	TAM	CAR	BRN	KIR	NRK	VIS	SBO	P50*
Raw Model	83.0	68.2	69.1	123.8	89.7	150.8	83.4	84.8	86.2	193.8	103.3
eQM-T	43.1	37.9	27.6	41.9	62.1	99.4	71.2	67.5	67.9	54.2	57.3
eQM-CS	29.4	36.0	27.1	34.4	55.5	94.9	71.0	64.6	64.4	43.4	52.1
KDM-T	39.3	41.3	22.8	42.6	68.8	82.5	70.3	66.5	67.9	52.1	55.4
KDM-CS	31.4	38.0	20.8	40.8	53.0	77.8	69.5	65.2	63.4	52.7	51.3
LIN-FIT	71.8	49.8	70.5	155.2	93.9	138.3	170.6	153.7	167.9	162.2	123.4
CDF-T	34.8	34.3	23.7	226.0	36.0	75.1	56.6	71.0	160.4	46.3	76.4
KDMR	36.5	37.4	28.3	133.2	43.3	74.4	58.0	51.5	142.7	43.0	64.8
QDM	31.5	37.4	26.5	415.9	40.7	81.3	63.3	59.0	214.9	45.5	101.6
SIM	63.4	103.8	53.6	96.8	141.6	119.4	144.3	110.7	144.1	77.3	105.5
SIMEQ	49.3	64.3	32.1	83.8	75.6	171.2	83.6	55.5	52.5	69.1	73.7

475 *Median of CPI for all sites

476
477

6. Sensitivity analysis

479 In addition to the benchmarking exercise, where the last complete year of ground
480 measurements was used for training the improvement method, a sensitivity analysis

481 on the training period was performed. This analysis was intended to determining the
 482 minimum period of time that should be used in the ground database for proper
 483 training. The sensitivity analysis has consisted in performing site adaptation to the 10
 484 datasets of table 2 using the eQM-CS method with training periods of 3 months, 6
 485 months, 1 year, 1.5 year and 2 years.

486

487 Figures 5 and 6 show the main statistical performance metrics for GHI and DNI (very
 488 similar results were found for DHI) compared to the uncorrected dataset referred to as
 489 model. It can be observed that a period of 3 months is insufficient to obtain significant
 490 improvement in most cases. Remarkably, such a short period tends to increase the KSI
 491 significantly, indicating that corrected data resulted in a worse similitude with the
 492 distribution function than the uncorrected data. For most of the cases, the sensitivity
 493 analysis indicates that 1-2 years of quality ground measurements are necessary to
 494 result in a general improvement of the solar radiation adapted data.

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499 Figure 5. Sensitivity of GHI performance to the training period duration.

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502

503 Figure 6. Sensitivity of DNI performance to the training period duration.

504

505 The sensitivity to a very large uncertainty in aerosol data (AOD, most importantly) or in
 506 the abundance of other atmospheric constituents in general can be also of interest,
 507 particularly for modeling DNI, which is the component strongly influenced by
 508 atmospheric aerosols and water vapor content in the atmosphere (Gueymard, 2012;
 509 Polo and Estalayo, 2015). The sensitivity analysis has been done by firstly generating
 510 satellite-derived DNI datasets for Carpentras, assuming different values (in terms of
 511 uncertainty in the atmospheric input) for the corresponding Linke turbidity factor. The
 512 latter's original estimated value at that site was adjusted in the range -30% to 30%.
 513 Assuming that the original TL value is perfectly true then the deviations can be
 514 considered as errors in the TL determination. Thus, regardless of the uncertainty in the
 515 original Linke turbidity factor, this sensitivity offers an assessment of the capability of
 516 site adaptation methods to correct situations with large overestimations or
 517 underestimations in atmospheric attenuating constituents. Here, the eQM-CS
 518 methodology was used for adapting or improving all the sensitivity cases. Figure 7
 519 shows the sensitivity analysis results in terms of MBD, RMSD and KSI as a function of
 520 the assumed error in the TL value used as input to the satellite model. In this case a
 521 significant reduction in bias, dispersion and KSI is achieved by the correction method,
 522 even for very large over- and under-estimation of the atmospheric turbidity. Likewise,
 523 removal of substantial part of bias observed in DNI datasets with inaccurate aerosol
 524 information has been also reported in studies with other correction techniques
 525 (Gueymard, 2011; Gueymard et al., 2012).

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529

530 Figure 6. Sensitivity to the Linke turbidity uncertainty. Performance metrics of DNI for
531 both the raw model and after correction with the eQM-CS method are shown.

532 **7. Conclusion**

533 Site adaptation of model-derived solar radiation time series is a general name for the
534 procedure of correcting and improving long-term modeled datasets by comparing
535 them to short-term overlapping ground measurements. Different methodologies can
536 be used for adapting a dataset of solar irradiance components to a specific site. Some
537 solar data suppliers have even developed their own methods. Many methodologies are
538 also inspired by bias removal techniques used in other fields of meteorology and
539 climatology. Two main families of methodologies can be identified according to the
540 purpose of the correction: regression-like methods and quantile mapping, from which
541 emerges also the combination of both as a third family. The former method focuses on
542 fitting by linear or multiple regressions the modeled data with ground data to an
543 equation able to be applied to the whole dataset. The quantile mapping techniques
544 work on the probability domain and correct the solar radiation data by fitting the
545 distribution function of modeled data to the distribution function of observational
546 data.

547

548 Under the framework of IEA-PVPS Task 16 a benchmarking exercise of site adaptation
549 techniques has been conducted by several participants in a blind exercise. Ten sites
550 and ten different measured and modeled pairs of datasets were prepared to test ten
551 different methods for site adaptation. Satellite-derived and reanalysis-based solar
552 irradiance data were included in the tested datasets to expand the variety of modeled
553 data as much as possible.

554

555 The results of this assessment of techniques have shown that most techniques are able
556 to produce improvement and some degree of correction of modeled data. There are,
557 however, situations where the quality of modeled data is already very high, so that it is
558 hard to get noticeable improvement in the site-adapted data. Nevertheless, quantile
559 mapping techniques have shown the potential of removing the bias observed in
560 modeled data. In addition, specific strategies that disaggregate the datasets according
561 to the state of the sky (clear, non-clear, ranges of clear-sky index, etc.) may offer better
562 performance. Likewise, the proper combination of techniques, such as sequential use
563 of multiple regression and quantile mapping, also resulted in significant improvement
564 in most situations.

565

566 In addition, a sensitivity analysis has been performed to study the proper training
567 period of ground data and the impact of very high bias in atmospheric input (AOD is
568 frequently overestimated or underestimated in some regions with a potential
569 detrimental impact on modeled solar radiation). Thus, it can be observed that ground-
570 based data time series covering periods of at least about one year seems to be
571 appropriate for proper training of adaptation methodologies at most sites. Moreover,
572 for the case of high bias in AOD-related quantities, quantile mapping based methods
573 have shown very good performance regardless of the uncertainty in the atmospheric
574 information used as input.

575

576 Finally, it is worth mentioning that it is difficult to establish a universal method or
577 procedure that works with the same efficacy in all possible combinations of sites and
578 modeled datasets. Good-quality ground data are always highly recommended for
579 proper training. Statistical methodologies can be very efficient in adapting modeled
580 data to a reference one, but in real conditions the better the quality of the reference
581 (ground data) the higher the potential improvement. Moreover, bad-quality
582 measurements could actually result in biased site adaptations, possibly more biased
583 than the original modeled dataset. In addition, a preliminary analysis of the
584 uncertainty at the site under scrutiny could be recommended before selecting one
585 method or another and before designing the proper subsets of data onto which the
586 site adaptation methodologies would be applied. It must be also remarked that even
587 though in this work we have shown mostly a pure statistical procedure it is
588 recommended to adapt only GHI and DNI and to compute DHI in a way that ensures
589 the consistency among the three components and the closure relation. In fact, this was
590 the procedure followed by Team 3 with two of the methods. Besides, it should be
591 pointed out that not all the correction methods have been tested in this work and, in
592 this sense, more methodologies, as model output statistics (MOS) and others, should
593 be investigated in future studies. The number and climatic diversity of sites used for
594 testing should also be increased to obtain results as universal as possible.

595

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602

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